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18

19 **Abstract**

20 Neuroscientific discourse on consciousness often resorts to ‘collection of elements’,
21 notwithstanding the Gestalt demonstrations against representing conscious experience as a
22 collection of sensory elements. Here I show that defining conscious experience as an object of
23 the category of conscious experiences, instead of as cohesion-less set of structure-less elements,
24 provides the conceptual repertoire—basic shapes, figures and incidence relations—needed to
25 reason about the essence of conscious experiences and the essence-preserving transformations of
26 conscious experiences. Viewed in light of the category of conscious experiences, designers of
27 user experience—in designing pre-conceptualized desired user experiences—are well situated to
28 contribute to the development of the science of consciousness.

29

30 **Keywords:** Category theory, Consciousness, Element, Figure, Gestalt theory, Mind, Object,
31 Perception, Relation, Set, Shape.

32 What is consciousness? Consciousness, according to Koch, “is everything you experience. It is
33 the tune stuck in your head, the sweetness of chocolate mousse, the throbbing pain of a
34 toothache, the fierce love for your child and the bitter knowledge that eventually all feelings will
35 end” (Koch, 2018, p. S9). This raises two foundational questions:

36 1. What is the nature of conscious experiences?

37 2. What is the nature of consciousness?

38 How are we to think of the totality of conscious experiences i.e., consciousness? How are we to
39 think of the constituents of consciousness i.e., conscious experiences? One obvious answer:
40 Conscious experiences are objects of the category of all conscious experiences and
41 consciousness is the category of conscious experiences. In other words, every conscious
42 experience has the essence of the category of conscious experiences, whatever the essence(s)
43 maybe. This characterization is in the spirit of asserting that a chair is an object of the category
44 of chairs.

45 Let us consider a visual experience: a face. A first-order approximation would represent the
46 experience as a feature list or as a point in a feature-space or as a set of features i.e., Face =
47 {eyes, nose, mouth} (Fodor, 1998). Sensory features are obviously structured, unlike the
48 structure-less elements of sets (Lawvere and Rosebrugh, 2003, p. 1). Equally importantly,
49 sensory features of a visual object are related to one another in specific ways resulting in a
50 cohesive object, which cannot be modeled by a set with its zero internal cohesion (Lawvere and
51 Schanuel, 2009, p. 146). Elementism, notwithstanding the Gestalt demonstrations (Albright et
52 al., 2000, p. S34), continues to be the default terminology as in analyzing “perceptual experience
53 into a collection of simple sensory elements” (Albright, 2013a, p. 19). Along similar lines, mind

54 is defined as a set of brain functions (Bunge, 1981, p. 68; Kandel, 2013, p. 546). The claim that
55 ‘mind is a set’ is repeatedly asserted in the textbook Principles of Neural Science (Kandel et al.,
56 2013, p. 5, 334, 384), which takes on added significance in light of its pedagogical value in
57 training neuroscientists. Of course, this terminology does not reflect any failure to recognize that,
58 in terms of the above example of face perception, the constituent eyes, nose and mouth, unlike
59 the structure-less elements of a set, are figures of various shapes; these figures constituting a face
60 are related to one another in specific ways (cf. Albright and Stoner, 2002). Nevertheless, it does
61 highlight the absence and the significance of having a conceptual repertoire that fits the reality of
62 conscious experiences. Here I put forward mathematical category (Lawvere and Schanuel, 2009,
63 p. 21, 135-148) as a construct suited for the study of consciousness. In line with the
64 commonplace understanding of the notion of category, a mathematical category consists of
65 objects all of which partake in the essence that is characteristic of the category; since every
66 object of the category partakes in the essence, the transformations of objects preserve the essence
67 (e.g. in the category of dogs, a transformation of an young dog into an old dog preserves the
68 “dogness”).

69

70 **Theory of Conscious Experiences**

71 What is the essence of conscious experiences? Continuing with our example of face perception,
72 an experience of a face can be said to consist of figures of various shapes: two eye-shaped
73 figures, one nosed-shaped figure and one mouth-shaped figure. Of these shapes, we can say that
74 eye, nose and mouth are the basic shapes, and their incidence relations determine the mutual
75 relations between various basic-shaped figures constituting the face (Lawvere and Schanuel,

76 2009, pp. 82-83, 250-253). When considering conscious experience in general, we may treat
77 sensory features (e.g. color, shape), modalities (visual, tactile, etc.), and emotion, among others,
78 as basic shapes. For illustration, anger (in conscious experience) can be considered as an
79 emotion-shaped figure (in the experience) just as redness can be thought of as a color-shaped
80 figure. The mutual relations between basic shapes, say, emotion and color, determine the mutual
81 relations between figures of the corresponding shapes (anger and redness).

82 Basic shapes along with their incidence relations constitute the abstract essence or theory of the
83 category of conscious experiences (Lawvere, 2003, p. 215, 217; Lawvere, 2004, pp. 10-12;
84 Lawvere and Rosebrugh, 2003, pp. 154-155, 235-236; Lawvere and Schanuel, 2009, pp. 149-
85 151, 369-370). First, every experience has the essence [of experiences] given by the basic shapes
86 and their incidence relations. Next, every experience can be represented as a structure formed of
87 basic-shaped figures and their mutual relations induced by the incidences of basic shapes (see
88 Fig. 4 in Posina, Ghista and Roy, 2017). Since every experience has the essence of experiences,
89 transformations of experiences are required to preserve the essence of experiences, and as such
90 are natural transformations (Lawvere and Schanuel, 2009, p. 378). Geometrically speaking,
91 natural transformations ‘do not tear’ the structure transformed (ibid, p. 210). Philosophically, a
92 natural transformation is: Becoming consistent with Being (e.g. biological growth; Posina,
93 2016).

94 What are we to make of the totality of all conscious experiences along with their essence-
95 preserving transformations? Objects along with essence-preserving morphisms of objects form a
96 category. With experiences as objects [with a given structural essence] and essence-preserving
97 transformations of experiences as structure-preserving morphisms of objects, consciousness—the
98 totality of conscious experiences—can be construed as a category of experiences (Lawvere and

99 Schanuel, 2009, p. 21, 152-154, 321-322). Note that any experience can remain the same
100 (identity transformation). If I went from sad to happy and from happy to detached, then I went
101 from sad to detached (composition of transformations of experiences). Along these lines, other
102 axioms and laws, which are required to be satisfied in order for us to talk about a category of
103 experiences, can be verified. Within this categorical framework, the structure of consciousness is
104 an external reflection of the structural essence of conscious experiences (Lawvere, 1972, p. 10).
105 More immediately, a category embodies a mode of cohesion (Lawvere and Schanuel, 2009, p.
106 146), which is the most basic attribute of conscious experience. For example, parts (hands, legs,
107 etc.) of a body have a mode of cohesion, which is different from the mode of cohesion of parts
108 (color, shape) of a perceptual object. Note that ‘part’ is both itself and its relationship to the
109 whole (Lawvere, 1994, p. 53).

110 As an illustration of theory of a category and its basic shapes, I present simple theories
111 (abstract essences) of conscious experiences (in the spirit of Lawvere, 1999). More explicitly, the
112 mathematical method, according to F. William Lawvere, “consists of taking the main structure
113 [of an object] by itself as a first approximation to a theory of the object, i.e. mentally operating as
114 though all further structure of the object simply did not exist” (Lawvere, 1972, pp. 9-10). With
115 ‘interpretation of sensation’ (Croner and Albright, 1999) as a theory of conscious experiences,
116 we obtain a category of two-sequential processes as the category of conscious experiences. Here,
117 the basic shapes are physical stimuli, neural sensation of stimuli, and conscious interpretation of
118 sensation. With conscious experience as an object of the category of two sequential functions, we
119 find that the objective logic intrinsic to consciousness is non-Boolean; for example, it has four
120 truth values (Posina, Ghista and Roy, 2017, pp. 172-174). Alternatively, we can take ‘action of
121 memory on sensation’ (Hopfield, 1982; Lawvere and Schanuel, 2009, p. 218) as a theory of

122 conscious experiences. With empathy and aboutness (or representation; Chalmers, 2006) as the
123 form and essence, respectively, of conscious experiences, we can define conscious experience as
124 a product: Empathy x Aboutness (cf. red circle = Shape x Color, i.e., object as a product of its
125 extensive and intensive qualities; Lawvere, 2007, pp. 44-45). Yet another example of an abstract
126 theory of conscious experiences is ‘particular as an exemplar of a general’ (Albright, 2013b, pp.
127 628-630), which gives the category of idempotents as the category of conscious experiences
128 (Lawvere and Schanuel, 2009, p. 106).

129 Given a category of experiences, how do we abstract the theory (essence) of experiences?
130 Theorization begins with measurements of properties of the objects of the given category.
131 Oftentimes, we find that there is small subcategory of properties (and their determinations)
132 within the category of all properties that constitutes the abstract essence shared by all objects of
133 the given category. This abstract essence in which every object of a given category partakes is
134 the theory of the given category (Lawvere, 1994, pp. 44-47; Lawvere and Rosebrugh, 2003, pp.
135 154-155; Lawvere and Schanuel, 2009, pp. 149-150; see also Fig. 5 in Posina, Ghista and Roy,
136 2017). In geometric terminology, we consider a subcategory of basic shapes and their incidence
137 relations, and examine if figures with objects in the subcategory as shapes are adequate to
138 completely characterize every object of the category and tell apart transformations between
139 objects (Lawvere, 1994, p. 49; Lawvere and Schanuel, 2009, pp. 370-371).

140

141 **Designing User Experience**

142 We now view user experience design in light of the category of conscious experiences. Let us
143 say you were to design an artifact that elicits a specific experience, say, religious experience

144 (Arbib, 2016). You imagine a category of artifacts (along with their mutual relations). Next, you
145 measure the values of their properties and examine their mutual determination. On further
146 examination, you find within this category of properties (and determinations), there is a
147 subcategory of properties, which is essential for the elicitation of the specific experience (cf.
148 raised gaze for religious experience). This essence is the theory of the category of artifacts
149 (eliciting the desired experience). Now that you have the essence ('raising the gaze') of the
150 category of religious buildings, you interpret the essence (theory) into a background category of,
151 say, brick and mortar to obtain a model of the theory of your imagined category of religious
152 buildings (Lawvere, 1994, pp. 44-47). Within this broad categorical framework, we can
153 accommodate distinct experiences elicited by different architectural designs (Albright, 2015, p.
154 201).

155 In the context of developing a scientific theory of conscious experience, it is important to
156 recognize change-of-experience as intrinsic to the practice of design. Neuroscientists vary stimuli
157 and examine the corresponding changes in conscious experience. So do user-experience
158 designers. Designers of user experience, by way of changing the basic shapes (e.g. sensory
159 features, modalities) and their incidence relations constituting the essence or theory of desired
160 experiences, are designing experiences ranging from ordinary experiences with the usual subject-
161 object divide and all the way to aesthetic and spiritual experiences variously described as 'figure-
162 sans-background', 'disappearing into appearance' or 'losing oneself' (cf. music; Posina, 2017).
163 Here, material objects are designed to elicit a specific (pre-conceptualized) experience. In
164 designing experience, design subsumes specification of the experience (in terms of figures of
165 various basic shapes and their incidences) and its essence (aboutness)-preserving transformations
166 from and to experiences of the category of experiences. Since theory is the essence of practices

167 extracted from a conscious participation in the practice (Lawvere, 2003, p. 215), a theory of
168 experience can be abstracted from conscious participation in the practice of designing user
169 experiences. Furthermore, changing theories and the induced changes in experiences are integral
170 to designing user experiences. Equally importantly, the wealth of empirical data accumulated in
171 designing user experiences is a valuable resource to draw upon in testing for the adequacy of
172 theories of consciousness.

173

174 **Conclusions**

175 I defined conscious experience as an object of the category of conscious experiences, which
176 aligns with the intuitions engendered by our everyday interactions with things (cf. a table is an
177 object of a category of tables). It is fascinating to note that the most advanced scientific
178 understanding of object (as an object of a category of objects; Lawvere, 2015) is in accord with
179 our ordinary experience. The category of conscious experiences provides the conceptual
180 repertoire—basic shapes, figures and incidences—needed to develop an adequately explicit
181 theory of conscious experience. In doing so, it brings into focus the significance of user
182 experience design in the development of a comprehensive theory of consciousness.

183

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193 **References**

- 194 Albright, T. D. (2013a). The Veiled Christ of Cappella Sansevero: On art, vision and reality.
195 *Leonardo* 46, 19-23.
- 196 Albright, T. D. (2013b). High-level visual processing: Cognitive influences. In *Principles of*
197 *Neural Science*, E. R. Kandel et al., eds. (New York: McGraw Hill Education), pp. 621-637.
- 198 Albright, T. D. (2015). Neuroscience for architecture. In *Mind in Architecture: Neuroscience,*
199 *Embodiment, and the Future of Design*, S. Robinson and J. Pallasmaa, eds. (Cambridge, MA:
200 The MIT Press), pp. 197-243.
- 201 Albright, T. D., Jessell, T. M., Kandel, E. R., and Posner, M. I. (2000). Neural science: A century
202 of progress and the mysteries that remain. *Neuron* 25, S1-S55.
- 203 Albright, T. D., and Stoner, G. R. (2002). Contextual influences on visual processing. *Annu Rev*
204 *Neurosci.* 25, 339-379.
- 205 Arbib, M. A. (2016). When brains design/experience buildings: Architectural patterns for a good
206 life. In *Cultural Patterns and Neurocognitive Circuits*, J. W. Vasbinder and B. Gulyas, eds.
207 (Singapore: World Scientific Publishers), pp. 111-140.
- 208 Bunge, M. (1981). *Scientific Materialism* (Boston, MA: D. Reidel Publishing Company).
- 209 Chalmers, D. J. (2006). The representational character of experience. In *The Future for*
210 *Philosophy*, B. Leiter, ed. (New York: Oxford University Press), pp. 153-181.
- 211 Croner, L. J., and Albright, T. D. (1999). Seeing the big picture: Integration of image cues in the
212 primate visual system. *Neuron* 24, 777-789.

- 213 Fodor, J. (1998). When is a dog a DOG? *Nature* 396, 325-327.
- 214 Hopfield, J. J. (1982). Neural networks and physical systems with emergent collective
215 computational abilities. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 79, 2554-2558.
- 216 Kandel, E. R. (2013). The new science of mind and the future of knowledge. *Neuron* 80, 546-
217 560.
- 218 Kandel, E. R., Schwartz, J. H., Jessell, T. M., Siegelbaum, S. A., and Hudspeth, A. J. (2013).
219 *Principles of Neural Science* (New York: McGraw Hill Education).
- 220 Koch, C. (2018). What is consciousness? *Nature* 557, S9-S12.
- 221 Lawvere, F. W. (1972). *Perugia Notes: Theory of Categories over a Base Topos* (Perugia, Italy:
222 *Universita' di Perugia*).
- 223 Lawvere, F. W. (1994). Tools for the advancement of objective logic: Closed categories and
224 toposes. In *The Logical Foundations of Cognition*, J. Macnamara, and G. E. Reyes, eds. (New
225 York, NY: Oxford University Press), pp. 43-56.
- 226 Lawvere, F. W. (1999). Kinship and mathematical categories. In *Language, Logic, and Concepts*,
227 P. Bloom, R. Jackendoff, and K. Wynn, eds. (Cambridge, MA: MIT Press), pp. 411-425.
- 228 Lawvere, F. W. (2003). Foundations and applications: Axiomatization and education. *The*
229 *Bulletin of Symbolic Logic* 9, 213-224.
- 230 Lawvere, F. W. (2004). Functorial semantics of algebraic theories and some algebraic problems
231 in the context of functorial semantics of algebraic theories. *Reprints in Theory and Applications*
232 *of Categories* 5, 1-121.

- 233 Lawvere, F. W. (2007). Axiomatic cohesion. *Theory and Applications of Categories* 19, 41-49.
- 234 Lawvere, F. W. (2015). Alexander Grothendieck and the modern conception of space.
- 235 http://sweet.ua.pt/dirk/ct2015/abstracts/lawvere_b.pdf.
- 236 Lawvere, F. W., and Rosebrugh, R. (2003). *Sets for Mathematics* (Cambridge, UK: Cambridge
237 University Press).
- 238 Lawvere, F. W., and Schanuel, S. H. (2009). *Conceptual Mathematics: A First Introduction to*
239 *Categories* (Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press).
- 240 Posina, V. R. (2016). Truth through nonviolence. *GITAM Journal of Gandhian Studies* 5, 143-
241 150.
- 242 Posina, V. R. (2017). Symbolic conscious experience. *Tattva - Journal of Philosophy* 9, 1-12.
- 243 Posina, V. R., Ghista, D. N., and Roy, S. (2017). Functorial semantics for the advancement of the
244 science of cognition. *Mind & Matter* 15, 161-184.